

Development of the GBC White Paper on Sustainability

GBC Board Working Group on Sustainability

In 2022, the Global Biodata Coalition (GBC) established two Board Working Groups that brought together senior representatives from GBC Member and Observer organisations to discuss key challenges relevant to GBC’s mission. One working group focused on Sustainability and the other on Open Data Strategies.

The Sustainability Working Group included experts from several GBC partner funders and resource providers. Its membership is listed below

Membership of the GBC Board Working Group on Sustainability

Name	Affiliation
Warwick Anderson (Chair)	Chair of GBC Board of Funders
Christophe Dessimoz	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (representing the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation, SERI)
Steve Ellis	US National Science Foundation (NSF)
Susan Gregurick	US National Institutes of Health (NIH)
Christiane Hertz-Fowler	Wellcome
Prashant Mathur	National Centre for Disease Informatics and research, India
Rowan McKibben	UK Research & Innovation (UKRI)
Claire O’Donovan	EMBL-EBI
Valérie Thibaudeau	Inserm, France
Daryl Waggott	Genome Canada

The Sustainability Working Group was tasked with exploring ways that funders could cooperate to support the global biodata resource infrastructure in a more sustainable manner. It had two key objectives:

- **To identify and share best practice for individual funders** — the Group explored challenges faced by individual funders that support biodata resources, and opportunities for funders to share good practice and develop longer-term, more strategic and sustainable approaches to support the biodata resources that they fund.
- **To explore ways funders could cooperate internationally to sustain the global biodata resource infrastructure** — the Group developed a series of premises, principles and models for enhanced cross-funder partnerships to more equitably and reliably fund biodata resources

critical to the global life science and biomedical research communities and explored ways in which funders could cooperate to develop and sustain the infrastructure as a whole.

Based on discussions over a series of meetings, the Working Group worked with the GBC Secretariat to develop a Consultation Papers setting out the challenges for biodata resource sustainability, and presenting a series of options for enhanced cross-funder cooperation. These options were intended as a starting point for further discussion with GBC's stakeholders and communities — including research funders, biodata resource managers and the wider life sciences research community.

GBC committed to use outcomes to develop a White Paper setting out a policy proposal and planned activities through which GBC and its member organisations will work together to support the long-term funding and sustainability of biodata resources.

Sustainability Consultation Paper

The [Consultation Paper](#) developed by the Working Group set out options under three headings:

- a. Options for individual Funders in funding and sustaining biodata resources
- b. Principles and models for cross-funder cooperation to support biodata resources of global importance
- c. Options for cross-funder cooperation to develop and sustain the global biodata infrastructure

A central element of the Consultation Paper was a series of premises and principles, which were suggested as a potential basis for coordinated cross-funder efforts to fund and sustain biodata resources. The nine principles are listed in **Box 1** below..

Box 1 — Nine Principles proposed in the Consultation Paper

1. Those who fund life science research share responsibility for ensuring that data resources are sustained.
2. Life science research funders of all types should contribute to biodata resource sustainability.
3. All life science research funders should contribute through means that are appropriate to their cases.
4. Sustainability will be required both for existing resources and for new resources that are established in response to new data types and technologies.
5. Models of funding must not require payment at the point of use of biodata resources (submission, retrieval, etc.).
6. Models for sustainability must cater for cases where funds cannot move across national borders.
7. Biodata resources must develop governance structures that support the interests of funding organisations and the institutions that host biodata resources.
8. Sustainability across the biodata resource ecosystem depends upon the openness of data they hold
9. All biodata resources should have a clear strategy for sustainability, including appropriate succession plans.

The Consultation Paper then set out four initial models based on these Principles:

- **Model 1 (distributed funding sources support a biodata resource)**—international funders contribute to a common fund (in proportion to total research spend), which is then allocated between an agreed set of biodata resources via a centralised mechanism.
- **Model 2 (a biodata resource is operated by distributed personnel)**—funders pay for activities in institutions and staff at those institutions then contribute to resources globally in line with need, through secondments or dedicating part of their time to supporting resources based elsewhere.

- **Model 3 (components that make up a biodata resource are distributed)**—funders support institutions which contribute specific components, activities or functions of resources. Under this model, resources would be highly distributed with sub-components at a variety of institutions around the world.
- **Model 4 (biodata resources are operated from multiple locations)**—funders contribute to resources in-country (or at regional level) which serve researchers at regional level but are part of larger coordinated resources at global level.

Stakeholder Consultation Process

The Consultation Paper was discussed by the GBC Board of Funders at its in-person meeting in March 2023, and amended to incorporate the Board’s feedback. The GBC Secretariat then ran a targeted consultation process during 2023-2024 to gather feedback from key GBC stakeholders on the Consultation Paper. This comprised two main elements:

- **Group Discussions with key GBC Governance and Advisory Groups** — both Consultation Papers were discussed by the GBC Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) at an in-person meeting in July 2023. The GCBR Forum discussed the Sustainability consultation paper at its virtual meeting in September 2023. Members of the SAC and GCBR Forum were also invited to respond individually to the community consultation (see below).
- **Community Consultation** — the Consultation Paper was published on the GBC Zenodo channel and highlighted via a news item on the GBC website. Members of the community were invited to submit comments via a structured Google Form, which consisted of a series of questions inviting feedback on different elements of the paper. The Consultation was communicated via targeted email to key GBC stakeholder groups (including the Board, SAC, GCBR Forum, members of the GCBR Selection Process Review Group and key GBC partner organisations), who were in turn invited to cascade to their contacts and networks. The consultation was also highlighted via social media (X and LinkedIn). The Consultation period opened on 2 October 2023, with an original deadline for responses of 4 December 2023. This deadline was subsequently extended to 22 January 2024 and further communication activities undertaken to attempt to encourage further responses.

A total of 21 responses were submitted during the community consultation period = in terms of the demographics of respondents:

- 13 responses were from individuals and eight were on behalf of organisations. The eight organisational responses included four from biodata resources, two from infrastructure organisations running databases and services and two from international standards bodies.
- Ten of 21 respondents indicated that their primary role was as an academic researcher. A further two identified as specialist data managers, curators or stewards; two more as engaged in policy or standards development; and one as a research funder. The remaining six respondents all indicated they either managed data resources or worked for organisations providing digital infrastructure and resources.
- Seven respondents were based in the USA, six in the UK and three in Canada. There were additional respondents from France, Germany, Switzerland, China and Australia.

Summary of Consultation Feedback

The community consultation and discussions from GBC advisory groups provided a large amount of valuable feedback on the Consultation Paper. The 21 responses to the community consultation

were of a very high quality, providing extensive and thoughtful feedback from a range of stakeholders engaged in the field.

Much of the feedback on the Consultation Paper was very positive and provided assurance that the options set out in the Paper provided a sound basis for GBC to move forward to build cooperative approaches to enhance sustainability of the global biodata infrastructure. The vast majority of respondents to the community consultation (16 of 19 who completed the relevant question on the web form) felt that the consultation paper provided a good summary of the challenges and need for biodata resource sustainability, with no major omissions.

The proposed Premises and Principles for cross-funder cooperation to sustain biodata resources formed the centrepiece of the Consultation Paper, and there was a strong consensus that these were highly valuable. In the community consultation, a majority of respondents (16 of 19) indicated that they would endorse the principles as they stand or with minor revisions. The SAC also strongly endorsed the nine principles which it felt could form the basis for communications and advocacy to enhance funder engagement in GBC and biodata resource sustainability more broadly. It placed a particular emphasis on the first principle, around the shared responsibility of life science research funders in ensuring the sustainability of data resources

There was some useful feedback on the Principles — mostly relatively minor points of clarification. The one substantive area of comment was around whether Principle 5 (that resources be free to access at the point of use for all users) was viable or fair. There was a feeling from a small number of respondents that funders should not restrict the exploration of models involving payment from commercial users. The SAC also advised that funders should not rule out any approach.

There was a good deal of considered feedback on the initial models for cross-funder cooperation set out in the Consultation Paper, although opinions on viability of the various models varied and it is clear that all models present significant challenges.

- Several respondents indicated a strong preference for model 1 (pooling funding), suggesting it was the most viable mechanism and held the potential to move things away from the current fragmented and piecemeal funding landscape. Other respondents, however, noted the significant challenges in terms of funders being willing to cede sovereignty and reach consensus on which resources to support, particularly if funding is limited.
- A second slightly smaller group of respondents indicated a preference for Model 3 (resources made up of distributed components) and/or Model 4 (biodata resources operate from multiple locations), with a particular preference for a variation of Model 4 with coordination at regional level. This was in part pragmatic given the perceived challenges with pooled funding approaches highlighted above, but was also based on examples of existing resources (with wwPDB, UniProt and Galaxy highlighted) which were seen to have successfully adopted similar approaches. Challenges with these models were also acknowledged, however, particularly in terms of avoiding duplication of components and in the potential for these approaches to create additional complexities in funding reaching biodata resources.

There was a very strong steer, particularly from the SAC but also reflected in the feedback of the GCBR Forum and individual respondents, that existing modes of funding would not scale. It was felt that addressing the challenge of biodata resource sustainability would in the longer term require more innovative and novel approaches. This should draw on experience from other sectors (including commercial models) and disciplines outside the life sciences, such as economics.

There was strong agreement that GBC should seek to strengthen its role in coordinating cross-funder discussions to sustain the global biodata infrastructure, including::

- working actively to expand the number of funders engaged and cooperating in efforts to enhance biodata resource sustainability, including through campaigns based on the principles set out in the consultation document.
- providing leadership in identifying and considering emerging needs for the biodata infrastructure as a whole, in light of scientific and technical needs.
- providing resources and support to individual funders to develop clear policy approaches and take forward discussions at national and regional level to establish strategies for working collectively to support biodata infrastructure.
- helping funders to set clear and consistent expectations for biodata resources around business models and sustainability planning.